

Design of Hexaport Robot for Firefighting Operation in Hazardous Area

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Received : 15 Januari 2025

Accepted : 25 February 2025

Online : 25 March 2025

Abstract – Fire is one of the disasters that can threaten life safety and cause significant environmental damage. The rapid spread of fire and the toxic smoke produced can endanger firefighters when conducting rescue operations. Based on these problems, we designed an automatic firefighting robot. This robot is programmed to explore rooms one by one, detect and extinguish the source of the fire, then return to the starting point. This robot is built with at least eight different types of core hardware, including an Arduino Mega 2560 board. Based on the test results, the HC-SR04 sensor showed quite stable performance with an average measurement error of 1.2 cm, while the QMC5883L sensor worked less than optimally due to magnetic field interference in the pump. The average forward speed of the robot was 180 cm/minute, and the average rotation speed was 9.7 degrees/second.

Keywords: Arduino Mega 2560, QMC5883L sensor, HC-SR04 sensor, threaten life safety

Introduction

Fire is one of the disasters that can occur suddenly and has a very detrimental impact, both on human safety, the environment, and property assets. Fire incidents can be caused by various factors, such as electrical short circuits, human negligence, gas leaks, or natural disasters such as earthquakes. Fires that are not handled immediately can spread quickly, produce toxic smoke, and cause large-scale infrastructure damage. In addition, the fire extinguishing process is often high risk for firefighters, especially in narrow, closed areas, or buildings that are at risk of collapse. Therefore, technological innovation is needed to help the fire extinguishing process effectively, quickly, and safely.

In Indonesia, fire extinguishing is generally carried out manually by firefighters. This manual process presents a great risk because officers must be close to the source of the fire, which can endanger their safety. Toxic smoke produced from fires can also interfere with breathing and cause poisoning. In addition, difficult-to-reach terrain, such as high-rise buildings, factories with hazardous chemicals, or industrial areas that have a risk of explosion, further complicates the extinguishing process. Based on these problems, the development of an automatic firefighting robot is an innovative solution to reduce the risks faced by humans when extinguishing fires.

This firefighting robot is designed to automatically explore the fire area, detect the source of the fire, and extinguish it by spraying water or other fire extinguishing agents. This robot is programmed to be able to move independently, avoid obstacles, and return to the starting point after the mission is complete. To achieve this performance, the robot is equipped with various main components, such as sensors, microcontrollers, and actuators. The HC-SR04 ultrasonic distance sensor is used to measure distance and prevent the robot from hitting walls or other objects. The QMC5883L compass sensor functions as a determinant of the direction of movement of the robot. The main microcontroller used is the Arduino Mega 2560, which is based on the ATmega2560, while the Arduino Pro Mini based on the ATmega328P is used as a secondary microcontroller to receive and process data from the compass sensor.

In addition, this robot uses the Hitec HS-645MG and Hitec HS-65MG servo motors as leg drives so that it can walk stably on various terrains. The DC water pump functions to spray water to the fire source, while a 3-cell Li-Po battery with a voltage of 12 V DC provides power for the entire system. The robot frame is made of aluminum iron material to provide strength and durability, and acrylic as the main material for the robot's body and head to reduce overall weight. The main objective of this project is to design and develop hardware and software for an ATmega2560-based automatic firefighting robot, which is capable of operating in high-risk fire areas without direct human involvement. By using this technology, it is hoped that the fire extinguishing process can be carried out more efficiently and safely, while reducing the risk of injury and death that may be experienced by firefighters.

Materials and Methods

The proposed system is designed in such way as illustrates in a main microcontroller block in Fig. 1. The flowchart of the proposed system is illustrated in Fig.2. The function of each block in Fig. 1 is as follows:

1. TPA64 Fire Sensor = Serves to detect the presence of candles/fires.
2. Compass Sensor QMC5883L = Serves to detect the direction of the robot so that the robot is easier to navigate.
3. Distance Sensor HC-SR04 = Serves to detect the distance of objects around the robot.
4. Arduino Mega 2560 = Arduino Mega 2560 serves as the main microcontroller on the robot.
5. Arduino Pro Mini = Arduino Pro Mini is used as a second microcontroller to receive compass sensor data.
6. Push Button = Functions as a robot start button.
7. Servo Driver = Serves to control the servo.
8. Servo = As a mover of robot legs (18) and fire sensor drive (2).
9. Relay = As a water pump switch.
10. Water Pump = Function to spray water towards the candle.
11. Led = Functions as an indicator.

Fig. 1. System Block Diagram.

Fig. 2. Overall system flowchart.

Additionally, the proposed and designed system is also assembled by considering the used components namely, Arduino ATmega 2560, Driver Servo, Ultrasonic HC-SR04, and Arduino Software Programming.

A. Arduino ATmega 2560

Arduino Mega 2560 is a microcontroller development house based on Arduino using the ATmega2560 chip. This board has a fairly large number of I/O pins, 54 digital I or O pins (15 of which are PWM), 16 analog input pins, 4 UART (hardware serial port) pins. Arduino Mega 2560 is equipped with a 16 Mhz oscillator, a USB port, a DC power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. This board is very complete, already has everything needed for a microcontroller. The solution for how to upload programs is simpler and faster, just connect the power from USB to the computer or via an AC or DC adapter to the DC jack [3][13]. Fig. 3 shows the physical board of Arduino ATmega 2560, and Table 1 listed the Characteristics of Arduino ATmega 3560.

Fig. 3. Board of Arduino ATmega 2560[12].

Table 1. Characteristics of Arduino ATmega 3560

Characteristic	Nominal Value
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage	7-12V
Input Voltage Limit	6-20V
Pin Digital I/O	54 (15 pins are used as PWM outputs)
Pins Input Analog	16
DC current per pin I/O	40 mA
DC current to pin 3.3V	50 mA
Flash Memory	256 KB (8 KB used for bootloader)
SRAM	8 KB
EEPROM	4 KB
Clock Speed	16Hz

B. Driver Servo

The servos used in the firefighting robot are 19 units, of which 18 are for the robot legs, and 1 for the water sprayer. So, with the large number of servos used, the digital pins on the microcontroller are not enough to control all servos. Therefore, in the design of the firefighting robot, a 32-channel servo driver is used. The 32-channel servo driver used is a servo driver produced by rt robot Ver 3.1. The characteristics of the servo driver can be seen in Table 2.

Servo motor is a DC motor with a closed feedback system where the position of the rotor will be informed back to the control circuit on the servo motor. The potentiometer is used to determine the limit of the servo rotation angle. On the other hand, the servo motor axis angle is adjusted based on the pulse width sent through the servo motor cable signal pin [4][14].

To operate or control a servo motor is different from a DC motor. Due to adjust the servo motor, it is necessary to provide a voltage source and control signal. The magnitude of the voltage source is related to the details of the servo motor used. On the other hand, controlling the rotation of the servo motor is tried by sending a control pulse with a frequency of 50 Hz with a time span of 20ms and a different duty cycle. Where to drive a 90o servo motor it takes a pulse with a duty cycle of one ton of positive pulses of 1.5ms and to drive a 180o servo motor it takes a pulse width of 2ms [4]. The principle work of servo activity is shown in Fig. 4.

Table 2. Characteristics of Servo Driver

Characteristic	Nominal value
Operating Voltage	5V
Servo Motor Input Voltage	4.2V~ 7.2V(According to the servo)
CPU	32bit
Baud Rate (USB)	115200
Baud Rate (Bluetooth, UART)	4800, 9600, 19200, 38400, 57600, 115200
Flash Capacity	16M
Number of Simultaneous	32
Servo Motor signal isolation	Yes
Size	63mm X 45mm
Communication	UART
Servo motor initial value	Default 1500
Support the Servo motor Type	9G~55G (3.3V~7.2V)

Fig. 4. Working Principle of Servo Driver.

C. Ultrasonic HC-SR04

An ultrasonic sensor is a sensor that has a function to convert physical quantities or sound into electrical quantities, and vice versa. The working principle of this ultrasonic sensor is quite simple, namely based on the reflection of a sound wave so that it can be used to define the existence or distance of an object with a certain frequency [5]. Ultrasonic sensors shoot ultrasonic waves towards certain objects. After the wave hits the object, the wave then reflected back to the sensor, then the sensor calculates the difference between the time of sending and receiving the reflected wave [6][9]. To get the distance from the HC-SR04 sensor, the formula is as follow:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \times v \times t \dots\dots\dots 1)$$

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \times v \times (T \times k) \dots\dots\dots 2)$$

S = The distance between the sensor and the object (cm).

t = Time from when the pulse is sent to the pulse received (μs).

T = Time taken by the microcontroller every 10μs from when the pulse is sent until the pulse is received (μs).

v = Speed of sound v = 34442.4 cm/s.

$k = \text{Time constant for AVR mode ATmega32} = 10s.$

The HC-SR04 is an ultrasonic sensor module that is commonly found in distance measuring devices. The HC-SR04 contains a pair of ultrasonic transducers, one of which serves as a transmitter, converting electrical signals into ultrasonic sound wave pulse signals with a frequency of 40 kHz, and the other as a receiver, receiving ultrasonic sound wave signals [7][10]. Fig. 5 shows the physical shape of the sensor.

Fig. 5. Physical shape of the HC-SR04 sensor[11].

D. Arduino Software Programming

IDE, which stands for Integrated Development Environment, is a development environment that is integrated. Since the Arduino is programmed to carry out the functions included in the programming syntax through this software, it is known as the area. The programming language used by Arduino is akin to C language programming. The Arduino microcontroller IC contains a program called Bootloader pre-installed that serves as a bridge between the Arduino compiler and the microcontroller before it is put on the market. The Arduino IDE is made using the Java programming language. Arduino IDE is also supported with a C or C++ library often called Wiring, which makes it easy to operate input and output. The Arduino IDE was developed from the Processing application, which was reconstructed into a unique Arduino IDE for programming with Arduino [8]. There are various Arduino programs that can support microcontroller programming. On the Arduino IDE menu, there are at least 5 menus that help in how to construct programs, namely File, Edit, Sketch, Tools, and Help, which are used to connect with files*. Ino (new, open, save, print). In the tale part, the software offers back notes on when to save and export and where to put errors. Fig. 6 shows the platform of the software.

Fig. 6. Arduino software preview.

Results and Data collection

It is very important that the HC-SR04 proximity sensor is placed properly on the robot. This sensor performs several functions, such as reading obstacles in front; reading the wall on the right using the right proximity sensor 1 and the right proximity sensor 2, and reading the wall on the left using the left proximity sensor 1 and the left proximity sensor 2.

The QMC5883L compass sensor is needed when the robot is in the home position, as seen in Figure 8. The function of this sensor is to help the robot find the right direction to exit the home position. The HC-SR04 proximity sensor is installed on the robot, as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. HC-SR04 Proximity Sensor is placed on the front and side views of the mechanical robot

The purpose of the sensor testing is to collect data from each block of the firefighting hexapod robot circuit to be used as a reference for making conclusions and to determine how well the system and tools work. Many tests and measurements have been carried out on the sensors. Table 3 shows the results of the HC-SR04 sensor test, and Table 4 shows the results of the QMC5883L sensor test.

Table 3. HC-SR04 sensor test results

Sensor Position	Actual Distance	Measured Distance
Front Sensor	40	38
Right Sensor 1	40	39
Right Sensor 2	40	39
Left Sensor 1	40	38
Left Sensor 2	40	38
Front Sensor	25	24
Right Sensor 1	25	24
Right Sensor 2	25	24
Left Sensor 1	25	23
Left Sensor 2	25	24
Front Sensor	10	9
Right Sensor 1	10	10
Right Sensor 2	10	9
Left Sensor 1	10	10
Left Sensor 2	10	8
Average error		1.2

According to the test results shown in Table 3, the sensor reading inaccuracy at a distance of 45 cm was 1.6 cm, the sensor reading inaccuracy at a distance of 25 cm was 1.2 cm, and the sensor reading inaccuracy at a distance of 10 cm was 0.8 cm. Thus, the HC-SR04 sensor reading has an average inaccuracy of about 1.2 cm assuming the boundary wood is placed exactly at the specified distance. However, as a result of the HC-SR04 sensor measurement error, no significant problems were found during the robot development process.

Figure 8. Placement of the QMC5883L Compass Sensor Mechanic Robots

Table 4. QMC5883L sensor test results

direction	Corner	read	Error
1	150°	150°	0°
2	240°	254°	+14°
3	330°	336°	+6°
4	61°	50°	-11°
1	46°	46°	0°
2	136°	142°	+6°
3	226°	244°	+18°
4	316°	326°	+10°

Table 4 shows the QMC5883L compass sensor error values which are somewhat unpredictable at various measurement angles. This occurs when a large enough magnetic field interferes with the sensor generated by the water pump. The magnetic field measured by the Android application called Magnetic Field Sensor reaches 1000 uT. Initially, it was expected that the use of a compass would provide precise navigation quality, which makes this an important issue in robot design. As a result, the compass sensor is used in this design only at certain times. For example, when the robot wants to face direction 1, which prevents errors during testing.

Conclusion

The robot has the ability to complete the sample space of the real arena in an average time of 159 seconds. The robot has the ability to walk in the corridor, enter the room, and perform diffuse spraying in a directed manner. To maximize the robot's navigation capabilities, the compass sensor and distance sensor must be of higher quality.

Acknowledgment

The authors are very grateful to experiences the funding of DIPA PNL 2021 through the research and the output is this paper that we submitted to the Int. J of Mechanical, Materials and Industrial Engineering

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